

Predicting SAR Coherent Change Detection Error from Quantizer Design

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INTRODUCTION

Among the many unique characteristics of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery, the data's complex and coherent nature is one of the most valuable. Coherent processing of SAR images allows for the detection of small changes, enabling detailed terrain maps or sensitive change detection algorithms. With the emergence of commercial SAR satellites, the transmission of SAR images from orbit to the ground for analysis has highlighted the importance of well-tailored compression algorithms. Not only should an ideal compression algorithm be matched to the data's statistics for ideal rate-distortion performance but also the distortion model should reflect the most sensitive use-cases for the product.

Prior work has been pursued in studying and modelling distortion for sensitive SAR use-cases, including [1-7]. Notably, [1] derived impactful analytical relationships between quantization and coherent change detection (CCD) that seem to be under-utilized in literature. The present work demonstrates an alternative formulation of the research in [1] that emphasizes a very simple relationship between quantization configuration and CCD error, enabling the ability to monitor product usability as easily as other common figures of merit. The second section of this paper derives the relationship between phase error and coherent change detection. The third section introduces quantization error into this analytical relationship and applies a specific quantizer to demonstrate the simplification of the metric. Experimental results are shown in Section Four to demonstrate how this can be used for predicting coherent change detection error. Finally, the paper closes with conclusions and remarks on areas of future work.

SIMPLIFYING THE TRADITIONAL CCD METRIC

A popular statistic for SAR coherent change detection, or coherency in general, is the Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ). $M \times M$ and $L \times L$ subsections of complex images X and Y are used to estimate the local ρ may be traditionally expressed and implemented as:

$$\rho(X, Y) = \frac{E\{\Re\{YX^*\}\}}{\sqrt{E\{XX^*\}}\sqrt{E\{YY^*\}}} = \frac{\frac{1}{M} \sum_m \Re\{YX^*\}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{L} \sum_l \Re\{XX^*\}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{L} \sum_l \Re\{YY^*\}}} \quad (1)$$

Typical change detection may leverage independent collections of the same scene as X and Y to identify changes over that timespan. This is computationally performed over localized $M \times M$ and $L \times L$ areas of the images. Using the convention of $X = x_r + ix_i = |X|(\cos(\theta_x) + i \sin(\theta_x))$, it may be further decomposed:

$$\begin{aligned} \Re\{XX^*\} &= x_r^2 + x_i^2 \\ \Re\{YY^*\} &= y_r^2 + y_i^2 \\ \Re\{YX^*\} &= |X||Y|(\cos(\theta_x)\cos(\theta_y) + \sin(\theta_x)\sin(\theta_y)) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

These decompositions, with an added restriction of $M=L$, yields the following expression:

$$\rho(X, Y) = \frac{\sum_m |X||Y| (\cos(\theta_x)\cos(\theta_y) + \sin(\theta_x)\sin(\theta_y))}{\sqrt{\sum_m x_r^2 + x_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_m y_r^2 + y_i^2}}$$

Contributions of the magnitude and phase components within the detection statistic are clearly identified. Since we are primarily concerned with the contribution of phase errors, isolating the phase component provides:

$$\rho(\theta_x, \theta_y) = \sum_m \cos(\theta_x)\cos(\theta_y) + \sin(\theta_x)\sin(\theta_y) \quad (3)$$

Intuitively, this correlation provides a maxima of 1 when X and Y share identical phases and the expression resolves into the Pythagorean identity. Alternatively, when X and Y are out-of-phase by π , the value is 0. An analytical "sweep" of potential relationships between X and Y phases is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: a) CCD estimate as a function of the phases of X and Y . b) CCD estimate as a function of the phase error between X and Y .

For the purposes of this paper, however, we do not particularly care what Y is, only that it conforms to the CCD null hypothesis of being very similar to X . As such, we may remodel Y as being X with an error term:

$$\theta_y = \theta_x + \theta_\varepsilon$$

Treating Y as a distorted version of X further simplifies the expression since it becomes invariant to X 's specific phase:

$$\rho(\theta_\varepsilon) = \sum_m \cos(\theta_x) \cos(\theta_x + \theta_\varepsilon) + \sin(\theta_x) \sin(\theta_x + \theta_\varepsilon)$$

and

$$\rho(\theta_\varepsilon) = \sum_m \cos(\theta_\varepsilon) \quad (4)$$

The implication of this final simplification is that when the Pearson correlation coefficient is applied to two scenes for the purposes of CCD, the losses in correlation can be modelled solely as a function of phase error, which is the indicator of change. In the context of image compression, a rate-distortion model can maintain custody of each image's quality with respect to coherent change detection by monitoring phase error. Plotted in Figure 1b is the correlation coefficient as a function of phase error, as shown in (4). This expression does indeed seem suspiciously simple; however, as will be discussed in section 4, this can have useful impact on monitoring and reporting SAR image compression error.

INDEPENDENT PHASE DISTORTIONS IN CCD

Assuming a single image will be compressed and compared to a pristine reference is impractical. Remote systems will compress every image that is collected for efficient transmission and storage; therefore, (3) needs to reflect the total error due to compression from both X and Y . To accomplish this, we can allow the phase changes due to compression differences (θ_Q) between X and Y to be:

$$\tilde{\theta}_\varepsilon = \theta_\varepsilon + \theta_Q$$

The quantized phase change between X and Y can be defined through the design of the quantizer. An N -bit uniform scalar quantizer applied to a SAR image's phase component imposes a bin spacing of

$$\Delta_\theta = \frac{2\pi}{2^N} \quad (5)$$

Knowing that the phase distribution of a SAR image is uniform, the mean-square reconstruction error for every bin is identical and follows the form outlined in [8]

$$MSE_\theta = \frac{\Delta_\theta^2}{12} 2\sigma^2 \quad (6)$$

where $\frac{\Delta_\theta^2}{12}$ is the quantizer's distribution variance and $2\sigma^2$ is the weighted variance of the phase distribution. Plugging (5) into (6) yields:

$$MSE_{\theta}(N) = \frac{\pi^4}{9 * 2^{2N-1}} = \tilde{\theta}_{\epsilon}^2$$

This expression captures the distortion of an N -bit uniform quantizer applied to a uniform phase distribution and is a useful model for the phase error encountered when compressing the two SAR images X and Y . Note that if an identical quantization scheme is applied to X and Y , then the distortion model is equivalent for both. Assuming both X and Y are compressed using an identical N -bit uniform quantizer, the square root of MSE yields RMSE ($\tilde{\theta}_{\epsilon}$), and simplifies to:

$$\rho_Q(N) = \cos\left(\frac{\pi^2}{3 * 2^{N-0.5}}\right) \quad (7)$$

Not only is this expression for $\rho_Q(N)$ noteworthy in its simplicity, but it is invariant relative to X and Y as long as X and Y are compressed using the same quantizer and the phase distributions are uniform. This metric defines compression-induced distortion to CCD based only on the quantizer's design relative to the input data's statistics and not the specific data being compressed. If the input data's statistics are stationary and the quantizer is static, then this error is valid across all images. To demonstrate that this expression is useful for estimating phase compression-induced error into coherent change detection, quantitative results are needed.

TEST RESULTS ON AIRBORNE SAR DATA

The publicly accessible GOTCHA Coherent Change Detection and Compression challenge dataset [9] exists to provide opportunities to conduct data compression research within the context of sensitive coherent SAR processing. Twelve complex floating-point images formed from independent passes of the same scene may be co-processed to form a CCD product. Shown in Fig. 2 are two example detected images and the CCD product of the two.

Fig. 2: Pair of complex SAR images (shown as detected) with the coherent change detection result between the two. Notice the walking path through grass on the left that is not visible in the detected products but easily identified in the CCD product.

All twelve images have magnitude and phase components compressed across a range of rates $N=\{8,7,6,5,4,3,2\}$. Phase components are quantized using a static uniform linear quantizer and magnitude components are compressed using a log-power quantizer. The images are then dequantized and reconstructed using the maximum likelihood reconstruction point. The independently compressed and reconstructed images are then selected in nonrepeating pairs to form 45 separate test CCD products. CCD products are formed exclusively between images with identical quantization resolutions. The utilized expression for calculating the CCD is the classical Pearson correlation coefficient in (1). The difference between the compressed CCD result ρ_C and the raw CCD ρ should be equivalent to $1 - \rho_Q$ from expression X.

Shown in Fig. 3 are CCD products of 5-bit quantized log-power and phase components of X and Y as well as the CCD difference. As can be seen, the CCD is noticeably degraded using quantized versions of the test images. Each pixel is bounded between 0 and 1 to indicate the level of difference and similarity, respectively. The difference between this and the raw CCD product shows a maximum reduction in the test metric of 0.12, a large decrease. The mean of this image yields the average error due to compression, which is then plotted vs the quantization resolution in Fig. 4Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Degraded CCD product (left) after X and Y are compressed using 4-bit quantizers with the error between raw and degraded CCD products (right). Negative changes indicates a loss in coherency while a positive change indicates a gain.

Fig. 4 also plots the predicted degradation as a function of bitdepth. As can be seen, the predicted error, as determined by (8) trends fairly well with the measured error from 42 image pairs. There are degradations at lower quantization resolutions, which are a result of the assumptions made during the simplification of expressions no longer being valid, but this still provides usefulness in estimating the impact of quantization on coherent change detection based solely on the quantizer's configuration at practical resolutions.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The development of a metric for predicting CCD degradation based-upon image quantizer configuration has been presented and compared to test results. Despite being originally claimed in 2005 by [1], the community has largely ignored the concept that CCD distortion due to quantization can be predicted based-upon the quantizer design and not the specific images. As can be seen, improvements to the presented model are needed to make it more robust; however, this concept has immediate utility in improving compression algorithms for complex SAR images and integrating CCD into rate-distortion models. This general approach has potential for integrating less trivial quantization schemes and permitting CCD estimation for practical compression algorithms. It is also of interest to fuse this distortion metric with the distortion metric defined in [7] to create a change-detection specific optimization algorithm.

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Fig. 4: Scatter of tested mean CCD error as a function of quantization with the analytical model plotted.

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